

Appendix Table 1. MNI for samples with 100 or more faunal bones.

Only contexts with > 1 MNI for any taxa are listed here, all other fauna in contexts in Masson and Peraza chapter not listed here have MNI = 1.

Most common taxa: brocket deer, dog, iguana, peccary, turkey, white-tailed deer (WTD)

	Q-151	Q-162	Q-163	Q-163a	Q-54	Q-56	Q-57	Q-58	Q-61	Q-64	Q-66	Q-69	Q-70	Q-72
Brocket deer	2	3	3			6	2	2	4		4		3	2
Dog	2	6	2	2		6		2	4		2	2	2	14
Iguana	4	14	6	2		15	2	4	15		24	2	2	5
Peccary			2			3		2	2					2
Turkey	2	3	4			15	2	4	9		7	5	3	4
WTD	3	26	12	2		29	4	5	14	2	9	6	5	20
Total # of bones in sample	480	4358	2566	353		9638	444	696	4901	174	2855	454	530	2537

	Q-72a	Q-74a	Q-79	Q-79a	Q-81	Q-82	Q-83	Q-87a	Q-87a/88a	Q-90	Q-91	Q-92	Q-94	Q-95
Brocket deer	2			2	2				2	2	2	2	6	
Dog	3			7	4	2	2	2	2			2	2	3
Iguana			2	5	7	2		2	2	2	2	3	16	2
Peccary				2	2								4	4
Turkey			2	9	8	2	2	2		2			17	5
WTD	3	5	5	9	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	13	6
Total # of bones in sample	104	153	1996	2178	190	173	379	229	363	409	488	3578	598	4144

	Q-96	Q-97	Q-98	R-100	R-106	R-112	R-151b	R-158b	R-183b	Y-43	Y-44	Total MNI per taxa
Brocket deer			4	2		3	2			2		48
Dog			5									52
Iguana	4	10				4	7			2	4	136
Peccary		3				2						20
Turkey	2	12				13	4	3		4	2	112
WTD	2	19	2	2	2	12	4	5		6	4	214
Total # of bones in sample	344	5045	142	140	2058	1367	1042	136	851	313	260	

Other taxa with MNI > 1:

	Q-151	Q-162	Q-163	Q-54	Q-58	Q-70	Q-72	Q-79	Q-79a	Q-92	Q-97	R-106	Total MNI per taxa
catfish					2	2		2	2				8
Fish					2								2
gopher								3				2	5
Rabbit			2	3			2			2	2	2	13
Rabbit (cotton tail)						3	2						5
Stingray (Rajiformes)		2		2									4
Total # of bones in sample	480	4358	2566	9638	4901	2537	3746	1996	1996	3578	5045	2058	